

The impact of environmental, social, and governance performance on the firm's financial distress: An empirical study on the listed firms in Egypt

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Abstract

Sustainability is one of the core pillars for the success of any organization and a core concern across different fields. The Egyptian government issued Decree No. 108 that obligates firms to disclose their ESG (Environmental, Social and Governance) practices, this emphasizes the critical role of such practices in generating value for firms, improving the quality of information, and protecting the stakeholders' interests, and this study aims to empirically investigate the impact of ESG performance on the firm's financial distress. This study focuses on an emerging market, Egypt, and the study sample includes 62 non-financial firms listed on the Egyptian Stock Exchange (EGX100) from 2012 to 2024, using a fixed effect regression to examine the study hypotheses and to answer the research question. The results report a statistically significant positive relation between the ESG listing index and the firm's financial distress in addition to the significance of one of the

control variables, which is asset tangibility. Overall, this study provides two main contributions, first it extends the existing literature by presenting empirical evidence from an emerging market, second it strengthens the ESG measurement through using two measurements where one of which is an application to the recently issued decree which provides a practical insight for the ESG impact on the firm's financial stability in the Egyptian market.

Keywords: Sustainability, ESG Score, S&P/EGX ESG Index, Financial Distress

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1. Introduction

Sustainable practices witnessed a shift from being viewed as a financial pressure, to being an economic development and financial stability driver. Over the past years, challenges such as climate change, scarcity of natural resources, and social inequality have forced governments and firms to change the traditional approach, which focuses only on financial performance in the short term, and to focus more on the long-term financial performance with consideration to environmental and societal protection.

Therefore, sustainability has become a global trend hence, the United Nations (UN) created the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) consisting of (17) goals relating to human rights, environmental issues and corporate reporting. These goals encourage governments, firms, and financial markets to work together toward a balanced economy. Accordingly, the Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (SASB) has contributed by setting guidelines that help firms report their non-financial information in a Systematic way. These efforts have improved global awareness for sustainability and supported the link between business activities and long-term economic development (United Nations,2015).

Sustainability importance has thus increased around the globe, and especially for the emerging markets due their economic, social, and institutional challenges and many countries started created their own vision and agenda for sustainability. Focusing on Egypt, for the purpose of this study, sustainability is a key pillar of the national development agenda through Egypt's

Vision 2030, which seeks to achieve economic growth while protecting the environment, improving social conditions, and strengthening governance practices. Egypt has aligned its capital market with global sustainability initiatives, including the United Nations Sustainable Stock Exchange Initiative, which encourages listed firms to disclose their environmental and social impacts and to adopt responsible business practices. These efforts reflect Egypt's obligation to sustainable development and its intention to enhance market transparency and attract responsible investors (Abdelmoneim and El-Deeb,2024).

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) activities, when first introduced, focused on voluntary initiatives such as community development, employee care, and environmental protection. However, limitations in CSR reporting, due to its absence of standardization and comparability, led to the development of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) performance as a more structured framework. ESG performance provides measurable indicators that show how firms manage environmental risks, social responsibilities, and governance practices, and its importance lies in its ability to provide non-financial information that is not taken from traditional financial statements (Zhou et al., 2023).

The ESG includes three dimensions, these are: (1) the environmental dimension which reflects the firm's approach to resource use, emissions, environmental innovation, and climate-related responsibility, (2) the social dimension capturing the firm's relationship with its stakeholders, (3) the governance dimension, which is concerned with board structure, shareholder rights, executive compensation, transparency, accountability, and internal control mechanisms (Fonseca et al. ,2024).

In recent years, environmental, social, and governance (ESG) practices have become increasingly important for firms seeking to enhance their long-term sustainability and resilience. Stakeholders are placing growing emphasis on corporate sustainability performance as an indicator of a firm's ability to manage risks and create long-term value. Therefore, ESG performance has evolved from a voluntary corporate initiative into a strategic factor that may influence various financial Variables (Aboud and Diab, 2019). Adding to this, transparent ESG disclosure can improve reputation, reduce information asymmetry, lower the cost of capital, and support long-term profitability and it further provides valuable insights into risk management, ethical behavior, and the sustainability of future cash flows of the firms (Zhou et al., 2023).

A main step to sustainability reporting in Egypt was the issuance of Decree No. 108/2021 by the Egyptian Financial Regulatory Authority. This decree was a shift from voluntary to obligatory ESG disclosure for listed firms, with application starting in 2022. According to this

regulation, Egyptian firms are obliged to disclose environmental, social, and governance information in a standardized method. Making ESG disclosure obligatory reflects the increasing importance of nonfinancial information in the Egyptian financial market. Also, aims to increase transparency, protect investors, and improve the firm's responsibility (El-Deeb et al.,2023).

In emerging markets, where firms frequently face financing constraints, institutional weaknesses, and macroeconomic volatility, the relationship between ESG performance and financial distress is especially relevant.

Financial distress occurs when a firm experiences difficulty in meeting its financial obligations, potentially leading to bankruptcy or corporate failure (Altman, 1968). Distress can trigger operational decline, restructuring, loss of stakeholder confidence, higher financing costs, and eventual liquidation. In this context, ESG performance may act as a financial risk-mitigation mechanism because firms with stronger environmental responsibility, social engagement, and governance structures may benefit from better reputation, improved stakeholder trust, lower information asymmetry, and more favorable access to capital.

Prior empirical work produced mixed relationships given different contexts and different market conditions. The general argument, that stronger ESG performance is associated with lower financial distress risk, is supported by several researchers such as (Fonseca et al.,2024) and (Chen et al., 2024) reporting that better ESG performance is negatively associated with the probability of financial distress in normal periods, indicating that ESG practices can support managerial and investment decisions aimed at reducing financial risk. The evidence further show that environmental and social practices may generate more immediate benefits, while governance effects may require a longer time horizon to become visible. Other researchers reflected on the complexity of such relation and suggested a non-linear association, such as the work of (Lohmann et al., 2025) which reports a statistically significant U-shaped relationship between financial distress and ESG scores among listed U.S. firms. Their results suggest that some financially distressed firms may intensify ESG-supporting disclosures in order to manage ESG scores upward, potentially to obtain better financing conditions, attract investor confidence, or divert attention from deteriorating financial fundamentals. This finding is important because it implies that ESG scores should not be interpreted in isolation from the firm's financial condition.

For emerging markets, this issue critical as ESG reporting systems are still developing, and the comparability and reliability of ESG data may vary across firms. Therefore, examining the ESG-financial distress relationship in Egypt can provide evidence on whether ESG performance functions mainly as a risk-reduction mechanism or whether the relationship may be influenced

by disclosure incentives. This motivates the need for an empirical approach that considers the firm's financial characteristics and controlling for factors such as size, profitability, among others.

Despite the growing international literature, limited empirical evidence exists on the ESG-financial distress relationship in Egypt. This gap is important because Egypt represents an emerging market in which sustainability reporting, governance reform, and investor interest in ESG practices are growing, therefore, examining Egyptian listed firms provides an opportunity to assess whether ESG performance can reduce financial distress risk in a context witnessing institutional transition and developing capital-market practices.

1.2 . Research Aim and contribution

This research aims to address the relationship between sustainability performance and firm's financial distress, for firms listed on the Egyptian Stock Exchange (EGX), by asking a main research question; Does sustainability performance affects firm's financial distress?

The study contributes to the literature in three ways. First, it extends the ESG-financial distress debate to an emerging market context that remains underrepresented in prior studies. Second, it examines ESG performance as a potential mechanism for reducing financial vulnerability among listed firms. Third, it responds to recent concerns regarding the ESG measurement, particularly the implication of the new sustainability regulations by (FRA's degree 108) and applying two different measurements for the ESG which are the ESG score and ESG listing.

The findings are expected to provide practical insights for regulators, investors, lenders, and corporate managers to strengthen financial sustainability and responsible corporate governance in Egypt, while contributing to academic research on the relationship between sustainability and firms' financial Distress in emerging markets.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: section (2) literature review, followed by section (3) reflecting the data and methodology and section (4) presents the results and analysis, and finally section (5) concludes this work.

2. Literature review

This section provides a theoretical and empirical argument for the sustainability performance and how it is linked with different characteristics and decisions within firms. The subsections present the theoretical framework followed by presenting the ESG index in Egypt and presenting prior empirical work in the field which paves the way for the research gap.

2.1.Theoretical Framework

Several theories exist supporting the relationship between Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) performance and a firm's financial decisions and performance. The main theories include stakeholder theory, agency theory, Trade-off theory, and the pecking order theory.

The Stakeholder theory shows that firms are not only responsible for their shareholders, but they must also care about other groups like employees, customers, creditors, and society. This theory suggests that firms that manage these relationships well will have more success in the long term, reduce problems and improve the firm's reputation (Freeman,2010; Jorgji et al., 2024). ESG disclosure supports the idea that firms with good ESG practices are better at managing financial risks. The agency theory Focus on the conflict between managers and shareholders, and it suggests that ESG practices may reduce the agency conflicts by improving transparency which consequently impacts different financials such as reducing financing costs (Meckling et al.,1976; Veenstra and Ellemers, 2020). On other hand, the trade-off theory suggests that firms with high ESG performance often use less debt, and this is because ESG practices help reduce risks and protect the company's reputation, therefore, these companies do not need to borrow a lot of money to fund their business (Kraus and Litzenberger ,1973; Bae et al.,2011). According to the pecking order theory, firms prefer to use internal funds first, then debt, therefore, firms with high ESG performance usually have steady cash flows and higher levels of financial slack and this helps in funding new projects internally and thus, by using their own money and reducing debt, these firms can lower their financial risk (Myers and Majluf,1984; Boubaker et al.,2020).

This study can be effectively explained through the stakeholder theory, suggesting that firms that actively respond to the expectations of its stakeholders are more likely to build trust and stronger relationships, and such relationships can protect firms during periods of instability.

2.2.The Egyptian Environmental, Social, and Governance Index

Before ESG disclosure became mandatory, sustainability-related practices in Egypt were voluntary. Listed firms mainly relied on voluntary corporate social responsibility disclosures and corporate governance reporting, with limited consistency and no unified ESG framework across companies. Also, some initiatives helped increase ESG awareness in the Egyptian market, the most important one was the S&P/EGX ESG Index, which was developed to enhance transparency and responsibility among Egyptian firms. Research shows that companies listed in this index tend to show higher firm values, suggesting that the firms with high ESG practices can

lead to improved financial performance. This relationship confirms that applying ESG practices is a motivation for companies to improve and enhance their firm value (Aboud and Diab, 2018).

Moreover, the index works as a tool for investors to identify firms that are committed to sustainable practices, therefore influencing capital allocation towards more responsible businesses. The index's role in showing corporate social responsibility is mainly important in the Egyptian context, where there is a need for improved governance structures and social responsibility (Mohmed et al., 2019). However, inclusion in the index was limited and based on ranking rather than comprehensive and standardized ESG disclosure. Nonetheless, in July 2025, the Egyptian Exchange stopped the S&P/EGX ESG Index, reflecting the need to enhance the alignment of ESG measurement with global best practices.

This reflects a shift in Egypt's ESG practices, due to regulatory initiatives led by the Financial Regulatory Authority (FRA) to issue sustainability disclosure regulations under FRA Law No. 107 and its executive Decree No. 108 reflecting a growing obligation to improve non-financial transparency and corporate governance among listed firms.

Although these regulatory developments highlight the importance of ESG practices in Egypt, empirical evidence on their financial consequences remains limited. Existing Egyptian studies lack the studying of the ESG performance impact on firms' financial stability. This gap provides strong motivation for the present study.

2.3. The impact of environmental, social, and governance on Financial Distress

The relationship between Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) factors and financial distress has received great attention in recent years. Each dimension of the ESG may affect financial distress through a different channel. Environmental performance may reduce distress risk by improving resource efficiency, reducing regulatory exposure, and limiting environmental liabilities. Social performance may enhance employee commitment, customer loyalty, supplier relationships, and reputational capital, which can support revenue stability and operational resilience. Governance performance may reduce agency problems, improve monitoring, enhance disclosure quality, and limit managerial opportunism. Together, these mechanisms suggest that stronger ESG performance should be associated with lower financial distress.

However, the effects of ESG dimensions may not be identical. (Chen et al., 2024) report that environmental and social policies can show immediate positive responses when firms are operating under favorable conditions, whereas governance policies may require time before their

benefits appear. This implies that ESG dimensions should not always be treated as interchangeable.

Fonseca et al. (2024) provide broad international evidence that firms with better ESG performance have a lower probability of financial distress. This argument is particularly relevant for listed firms because firms with better ESG performance may be viewed as more transparent, better managed, and more capable of maintaining long-term performance. As a result, they may benefit from easier access to external financing, lower borrowing costs, and greater investor support. These benefits can directly reduce the likelihood of financial distress.

Binesh et al. (2025) explain the effect of ESG practices on financial distress in times of uncertainty on non-financial firms listed in the U.S market, and the results reflect a positive significant relation between ESG performance and Z-scores that lower the financial distress risk during the pandemic, suggesting that ESG practices can serve as a shield against financial instability. Similarly, the study applied on U.S listed firms by (Boubaker et al.,2020) examined the impact of CSR on corporate stability using a large sample of firms from 1991 to 2012 and found a significant negative relationship between ESG score and financial distress risk, which means when the firm increase the score of ESG that reduces the financial distress risk through increase the Altman Z-score. Further, exploring the Chinese market, (Tang, 2022) and (Zhou et al., 2023) suggest that high ESG scores function as a risk-management tool, improving a firm's financial stability and operational performance. Thus, ESG practices help Chinese firms keep financial health and avoid the probability of financial distress.

In emerging markets financially distressed firms may improve their ESG disclosures as a strategic move to improve their financial performance, although they care that such disclosures require financial resources that such distressed firms may lack. This relationship suggests that while ESG practices can improve financial distress, the ability to invest in these practices may be forced by existing financial challenges (Harymawan et al. ,2021). A study, applied on listed firms in Saudi Arabia, by (Alquhaif et al., 2025), reports a negative significant relationship between the ESG Performance and financial distress risk. This relation explains that the ESG performance improves stockholder trust, reduces the information asymmetry, transparency, and reputational risks, all of which enhance firms' financial stability. Moreover, other emerging market such as Indonesia, reports no effect of ESG performance on financial distress (Sihotang and Siregar,2025).

To conclude, the reviewed literature indicates that ESG performance can reduce financial distress through improved transparency, stakeholder support, access to financing, and risk

management. However, the relationship may depend on firm conditions, level of disclosure, and market condition. Moreover, most existing studies focus on developed markets or broad international samples, while limited evidence is available for Egypt. This creates a clear research gap regarding whether ESG performance contributes to reducing financial distress among Egyptian listed firms. Based on the theoretical arguments and prior empirical evidence, the following hypothesis and sub-hypotheses are proposed:

H1: Sustainability performance has a significant impact on Firm's Financial Distress.

- H1a ESG Score has a significant impact on the Firm's Financial Distress.
- H1b ESG Index listing has a significant impact on the Firm's Financial Distress.

3. Methodology

This section presents details about the data, research model, and the variables measurement tools used and this is presented in the following three subsections.

3.1 Data and Sample

This study has a population of firms listed on the Egyptian Exchange (EGX100), which consists of financial and non-financial firms. Banks and financial firms, counted (19), are excluded from the study due to their special regulation and accounting standards; further, firms with missing data, counted (19) as well, are excluded from the study. Therefore, the final sample includes (62) firms allocated on 14 sectors. The study period covers 13 years, from 2012 to 2024.

The study employs panel data as it aims to test for the variables under concern for different firms across different years. Secondary data sources were the main source of data as the ESG scores were derived from firms' historical annual reports and publicly available, ensuring consistency and cross-sectional comparability of sustainability performance across firms and years. In addition, Financial Data (Dependent and Control Variables) was collected from financial statements and annual reports, all were collected through the EGID (Egyptian Company for Information Dissemination) and the Thomson Reuters Refinitiv database, ensuring both local accuracy and international comparability.

3.2 Research Model

This section shows the research models that measure the impact of ESG performance through two different Variables which are ESG Scoring (Model A) and ESG index Listing (Model B), on the dependent variable which is financial Distress.

Model A is formed to test the impact of ESG Score on financial distress. Control variables are included to determine their impact on financial Distress.

Model A (ESG Score and Financial Distress)

$$\begin{aligned} z''score(EMS)_{it} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 ESG\ Scoring_{it} + \beta_2 SIZE_{it} + \beta_3 AGE_{it} + \beta_4 TANG \\ &+ \beta_5 TURN_{it} + \beta_6 INS_{it} + \beta_7 LBLOCK\ IQ_{it} + \beta_8 MANAGE_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \end{aligned}$$

Model B is formed to test the impact of the ESG listing index on financial distress. Control variables are included to determine their impact on financial distress.

Model B (ESG Listing and Financial Distress)

$$\begin{aligned} z''score(EMS)_{it} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 ESG\ Listing_{it} + \beta_2 SIZE_{it} + \beta_3 AGE_{it} + \beta_4 TANG \\ &+ \beta_5 TURN_{it} + \beta_6 INS_{it} + \beta_7 LBLOCK\ IQ_{it} + \beta_8 MANAGE_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \end{aligned}$$

Where: ESG Scoring: ESG score for firm-year, **ESG Listing:** Environmental, Social and Governance listing in S&P/EGX-ESG index, **Z'' score (EMS):** Z'' Emerging Markets score predicts financial distress, **SIZE:** firm size, **AGE:** firm age, **TANG:** asset tangibility, **TURN:** Asset Turnover, **IND:** industry sector, **BLOCK:** Block holders Ownership, **MANAGE:** Managerial ownership, ε : represents the error term.

3.3 Variables Measurement

The dependent variable under study is the firm financial distress, which is defined as a state where a firm struggles to meet its financial obligations, potentially leading to bankruptcy, and this variable is measured using Altman Z score for emerging markets. While the independent variable is the ESG performance measured using two measures: the ESG Score and ESG listing. Table (1) summarize all variables in this study with their measuring tools.

Table (1)
Variables and measurements

Variable	Code	Measurement	Reference
Dependent Variable			
Financial Distress (Altman Z''-Score EMS)	(Z-Score)	$Z'' - Score = 3.25 + 6.56 \left(\frac{Net\ Working\ Capital}{Total\ Assets} \right) + 3.26 \left(\frac{Retained\ Earnings}{Total\ Assets} \right) + 6.72 \left(\frac{EBIT}{Total\ Assets} \right) + 1.05 \left(\frac{Book\ Value\ of\ Equity}{Total\ Liabilities} \right)$	(Altman,1968; Altman and Hotchkiss,2010; Hassan,2022; Elewa,2022)
Independent Variables - The ESG Performance			
ESG SCORE	ESG SCORE	A continuous composite score derived from the aggregation of quantitative performance indicators (Stage 1) and qualitative policy disclosures (Stage 2).	FRA Decree NO.108; S&P/EGX Methodology (Deeb et al., 2023) and (Abdelsalam et al., 2025)
ESG LISTING	ESG LISTING	A dummy variable coded as one if the firm is listed in the ESG index; otherwise, it is coded as 0.	(Eldomiaty at al.,2016; Aboud and Diab,2018; Diab and Eissa,2023)
Control Variables			
Firm Size	FSIZE	log value of total assets.	(Bassiouny,2016; Aboud and Diab,2019; El-Deeb et al., 2023; Wahyuni et al., 2024)
Firm Age	FAGE	The number of years since the firm's incorporation.	(Coad et al., 2018; Rahman and Yilun,2021; EL-Hindawy et al.,2021; Gamal et al.,2022; Ushijima,2025).
Asset Tangibility	TANG	$TANG = \frac{Fixed\ Assets}{Total\ Assets}$	(Boubaker et al.,2020; Ateya and ali, 2023; Zhang,2025).
Asset Turnover	TURN	$TURN = \frac{Net\ Sales}{Total\ Assets}$	(Hussainey and Salama,2010; Shahwan,2015)
Industry	IND	A dummy variable coded as 1 if the firm is from manufacturing; it is coded as zero otherwise.	(Elbekpashyand ElGiziry,2018; Aboud and Diab,2019; Zaid etal.,2020; Mohammad and Wasiuzzaman,2021)
Ownership Structure	BLOCK MANAGE	<p>Blockholders Ownership: Percentage of outstanding shares held by investors owning 5% or more.</p> <p>Managerial ownership: Percentage of outstanding shares held by the Board of Directors and Executive Management.</p>	(Ould ,2020; Abdel Megeid,2021; Nguyen et al., 2021, Lutfiani and Hidayah,2022)

According to the obligatory disclosure requirements, issued by the Egyptian Financial Regulatory Authority (FRA) under Decree No. 108, the FRA and Egypt for Information Dissemination (EGID) traced the ESG data back by time to reflect the newly issued decree. Therefore, the total ESG scores for the EGX 100 are calculated according to the FRA ESG KPIs in Decree no 108.

Further, the ESG LISTING is measured using a firm's membership in the EGX ESG Index. The variable uses a dummy variable coded as (1) if the firm is listed in the ESG index; otherwise, it is coded as (0). This measure reflects whether the firm has received market recognition for its environmental, social, and governance practices based on the index's selection criteria. This study includes six control variables, namely: firm size, firm age, asset tangibility, asset turnover, industry, and ownership structure.

4. Results and Discussion

This section presents all the findings after running different statistical tests. The analysis starts with the descriptive statistics, followed by the Pearson correlation analysis and testing for multicollinearity. Then the study runs the Hausman test since it's a panel data and finally, the results of the regression analysis are presented and discussed to see whether the hypotheses are validated or not. The analysis is done using the Stata program.

4.1 Descriptive statistics

The aim of this analysis is to describe the variables by showing the mean, minimum and maximum values and the standard deviation of the dependent and independent variables. Where, the independent variables in this research are ESG Scoring and ESG Listing. While the dependent variable is financial Distress (Z'' -Score) And the Control Variables are Firm Size (FSIZE), Firm Age (FAGE), Asset Tangibility (TANG), Asset Turnover (TURN), industry (IND) and Ownership structure through Block holders' ownership (BLOCK) and Managerial ownership (MANAGE).

Table (2) report that the Total ESG Score has a mean value of (123.6) with a standard deviation of (10.65), representing moderate dispersion around the average level of sustainability performance among the sampled firms. The minimum and maximum values range from (97.39) to (181), indicating means variation in ESG practices across firms and over time. This variation is important for panel data analysis and is consistent with prior evidence from emerging markets, where ESG performance is mixed due to differences in governance quality, disclosure practices, and firm age.

Table (2)
Descriptive Statistics

VARIABLES	Mean	Sd	min	max
ESG score	123.6	10.65	97.39	181
ESG listing	0.292	0.455	0	1
Z-SCORE	7.339	3.610	-2.861	18.10
FSIZE	6.477	0.729	4.400	8.552
FAGE	41.89	28.30	1	170
TANG	0.446	0.250	0.000122	0.943
TURN	0.662	0.693	0.000112	4.486
IND	0.441	0.497	0	1
BLOCK	0.631	0.197	0	0.998
MANAGE	0.0385	0.100	0	0.519

The ESG Index Listing variable, which is a dummy variable equal to (1) if listed and (0) otherwise, shows a mean of (0.292), indicating that approximately 29.2% study sample of firms has included in the ESG index. On the other side, the dependent variable, financial Distress has a mean value of (7.339), which means that, on average, firms fall within the financially safe zone. However, the presence of negative minimum values (-2.861) highlights that certain firm-year observations experienced raised distress, underscoring the relevance of examining financial stability dynamics in the Egyptian context. For the maximum of (18.10), minimum of (-2.861) and standard deviation of (3.61). The relatively wide range of Z-scores supports the suitability of this measure for capturing cross-sectional differences in financial health.

Finally, the control variables, First, firm size has a mean value of (6.477) and a standard deviation of (0.729), which means that, variation in firm scale among across the sample. For the maximum of (8.552) and minimum of (4.400). Secondly, Firm age averages (41.89) years, with a wide dispersion, reflecting a mix of long-established firms and relatively younger firms. Thirdly, Asset tangibility records a mean of (0.446), suggesting that tangible assets constitute a substantial proportion of total assets, a common feature in emerging markets where collateral plays a key role in financing decisions. Fourthly, Asset turnover has a mean of (0.662), indicating moderate efficiency in asset utilization. Fifthly, Industry, which is a dummy variable: 1 if the firm is from manufacturing; and 0 otherwise. Sixthly, Ownership structure variables reveal that block holder ownership has a relatively high mean value of (0.631), confirming the prevalence of ownership concentration in Egyptian listed firms, while managerial ownership records a low

mean of (0.039), consistent with prior evidence from Egypt and the MENA region highlighting limited managerial equity participation and dominant controlling shareholders.

4.2 Pearson Correlation Analysis

To assess for the correlation between the variables and determine whether there is a multicollinearity problem in the research model or not, Pearson's Correlation Coefficient is employed.

Table (3)
Pearson Correlation

	ESG Score	ESG Listing	Financial Distress	Fsize	Fage	TANG	TURN	IND	BLOCK	MANAGE
ESG Score	1									
ESG Listing	0.6199	1								
Financial Distress	0.0217	0.0036	1							
Fsize	0.4358	0.4176	0.3328	1						
Fage	-0.043	-0.0648	0.0297	0.0954	1					
TANG.	-0.0089	-0.0387	0.273	-0.0116	-0.1189	1				
TURN.	0.1601	0.0844	0.0313	0.007	-0.084	-0.1815	1			
IND	0.0536	0.0574	0.3188	0.0007	-0.0635	0.3059	0.2739	1		
BLOCK	0.1014	0.0947	0.0011	0.2782	0.174	-0.0088	-0.042	-0.0249	1	
MANAGE	0.0085	-0.0072	0.0025	0.0116	0.0017	-0.0457	0.2968	0.0646	-0.1676	1

Table (3) shows the direction and strengths of the relationships between all variables with one another. According to (Bryman and Cramer, 1997), Pearson's correlation between the independent variables is not reflected as a problem unless it is higher than 0.80. However, as long as the highest correlation in table (3) is still less than 0.80, so this confirms that there is no multicollinearity problem.

Another test is the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) as reported in table (4) below. The results indicate that multicollinearity does not pose a concern in the estimated models as the overall VIF values for both models is far from (10). Therefore, there is no multicollinearity problem (O'Brien, 2007).

Table (4)
Variance Inflation Factor

	Model A: VIF for Total ESG Score	Model B: VIF for ESG Index Listing
ESG score	1.29	1.24
FSIZE	1.35	1.34
FAGE	1.07	1.06
TANG	1.23	1.24
TURN	1.34	1.30
IND	1.26	1.24
BLOCK	1.15	1.16
MANAGE	1.14	1.16
Mean VIF	1.23	1.22

4.3. Hausman Test for Fixed Versus Random Effects

The Hausman test to determine whether to use the fixed effect regression or the random effect regression is carried out for a sample of 62 firms listed in the Egyptian stock exchange for a period from 2012 to 2024. As shown in Table (5), the study tested for two models, where model (A) uses the ESG score as independent variable and the results indicates a significant level of (0.0276) which is lower than the significance level of (0.05) and this indicated that the fixed effect regression should be used instead of the random effect. While model (B) uses the same dependent variable but having the ESG listing as the independent variable and the results indicates a significant level of (0.0364) and this indicates that the fixed effect regression should be used instead of the random effect as well (Amini et al. ,2012).

Table (5)
Hausman Test

		Coef.	Fixed Versus Random Effects
Model A	Chi-square test value	15.74	Fixed Effect model
	Prob > chi2	0.0276	
Model B	Chi-square test value	14.97	Fixed Effect model
	Prob > chi2	0.0364	

Moreover, regression diagnostics identified autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity problems, and these were solved using the cluster-robust standard errors using the Stata program to reach a reliable final regression model.

4.4. Regression results

Applying the fixed effect for model (A) and model (B) and using cluster-robust standard errors, table (6) present the final regression results.

Table (6)
Final regression for (ESG SCORE and ESG LISTING)

	(Model A)		(Model B)
	Financial Distress		Financial Distress
ESG Score	0.0202	ESG Index Listing	0.490*
	(1.48)		(1.68)
Firm Size	0.513	Firm Size	-0.157
	(0.37)		(-0.15)
Firm Age	-0.110	Firm Age	-0.0721
	(-1.26)		(-1.03)
Asset Tangibility	-5.378***	Asset Tangibility	-5.317***
	(-3.20)		(-3.48)
Asset Turnover	0.332	Asset Turnover	0.255
	(0.64)		(0.48)
1.Industry	0	1.Industry	0
	(.)		(.)
Blockholders' ownership	-2.341	Blockholders' ownership	-0.797
	(-1.37)		(-0.50)
Managerial ownership	1.075	Managerial ownership	0.319
	(0.41)		(0.13)
_cons	9.912	_cons	13.94**
	(1.48)		(2.59)
R Square	0.1138	R Square	0.1077
Prob>F	0.0692	Prob> F	0.0034
Robust standard errors in parentheses			
t statistics in parentheses			
* p<0.1, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01			

The Fixed-effects (within) regression for Model A is found to be highly significant for financial distress, with a significance level of the p-value equals to (0.0692), and the R-square for this model is (0.1138), which indicates that 11.38% of the within-firm variation in financial distress is explained by the independent and control variables. Moreover, Fixed-effects (within)

regression for Model B is found to be highly significant for financial distress, with a significance level the p-value equals to (0.0034) and the R-square for this model is (0.1077), which indicates that 10.77% of the within-firm variation in financial distress is explained by the independent and Control variables.

In Model A, one variable only reported a significant effect on the firm's financial distress, which is the asset tangibility as a control variable. The relation reported is a negative relationship with a coefficient value of (-5.378), this suggests that a higher level of fixed assets leads to increased financial risk (lower Z-score). This result goes inconsistency with the study results of (Ateya and ali, 2023) which is an empirical study applied on non-financial firms in the Egyptian market.

The model indicates that the relationship between firm's ESG SCORE and financial distress is a statistically insignificant, although the estimated coefficient of ESG score is positive, suggesting that higher ESG score may be associated with higher Z-score which reduces the financial distress risk. Therefore, the hypothesis, H1a: Total ESG score has a statistically significant impact on the firm's financial distress, is Not accepted.

This result is consistent with the study applied on an emerging market by (Sihotang and Siregar, 2025) explaining the effect of ESG performance on firm value and financial distress on non-financial companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, and the results show no effect of ESG performance on financial distress. On the other hand, the results of this paper disagree with the findings of several prior work, as some report a positive relation such as the study by (Binesh et al., 2025), which explains the effect of ESG practices and financial distress in times of uncertainty on non-financial industries listed on U.S. listed firms and found a positive Significant relation between ESG performance and Z-scores which lowers the financial distress risk during the pandemic, suggesting that ESG practices can serve as a shield against financial instability.

Contrarily, several studies report a negative significant relationship between ESG Score and financial distress, one of which is the Study applied in Saudi Arabia by (Alquhaif et al.,2025) reporting a negative significant relation showing that firms with higher ESG performance have higher Z-score and that reduces the financial distress risk. Other studies supporting this negative relation are: (Boubaker et al.,2020; Lohmann et al. 2025).

In Model B, two variables reported a significant effect on the firm's financial distress, these are: Asset Tangibility as a control variable and the ESG Index listing as an independent variable.

The asset tangibility reports a highly significant negative relationship with financial distress with a coefficient value of (-5.317) which is similar to the result in model A and this is consistent with (Shahwan, 2015). While the second variable, ESG Index listing, reports a significant positive relationship with a coefficient value of (0.490), reflecting that when firms are listed on a sustainability index, this increases the Z-score which indicates a reduced probability of bankruptcy and an improved corporate stability. Therefore, the hypothesis, H1b: ESG index listing has a statistically significant impact on the firm's financial distress, is accepted.

This result agrees with the study applied on the S&P BSE 100 ESG Index, by (Singh,2024) that study explains the effect of listing on the ESG Index on financial distress and reports a significant positive relationship between a firm's listing on an ESG index and its Altman Z-score on Indian listed non-financial firms. This result also aligns with several studies applied on the Egyptian market such as the study by (Elewa,2022) and (Hassan,2022). And such result goes in conformity with the stakeholder theory.

While an ESG listing is a strong stability signal, its effectiveness is often depending upon the firm's operational costs and the broader macroeconomic environment. Thus, some studies report a negative relation suggesting that during periods of extreme economic volatility, such as the Covid-19 pandemic, the predictive power of non-financial indicators like ESG on financial stability may reduce, (Srouf ,2022), further the high costs associated with maintaining the sustainability standards required for index listing could potentially drain a firm's internal resources, leading to an insignificant impact on solvency (Z-score) in certain high-cost sectors, (Wahyuni et al.,2024).

5. Conclusion

This paper examines the impact of ESG performance on the firms' financial distress using a panel data analysis applied on 62 non-financial firms listed on the Egyptian Stock Exchange taking a period from 2012 to 2024, and applying two models, one that uses the total ESG score as an ESG performance indicator and the other uses ESG listing index.

The reviewed literature suggests that ESG performance can function as an important mechanism for reducing financial vulnerability. Further, firms with stronger environmental, social, and governance practices are generally expected to benefit from enhanced stakeholder relationships, improved transparency, stronger governance, better access to finance, and lower cost of capital.

The Egyptian context provides a valuable setting for this investigation. As sustainability reporting and ESG awareness continue to develop in Egypt, empirical evidence is needed to determine whether ESG performance contributes to reducing financial distress among listed firms. The final result for this study, show that there is an insignificant relationship between a firm's ESG score and financial distress (Z-Score), while there is a statistically significant positive relationship between a firm's ESG listing index and financial distress (Z-Score), suggesting that firms recognized by the ESG index exhibit greater financial stability and lower distress risk and this supports the second sub hypothesis.

This study is vital, both practically and academically. First, practically, the results would help the firm's managers understand whether ESG engagement would be increasing to the firm financial stability. Further, for investors and lenders, the ESG performance may improve investment decision-making by including the sustainability indicators into risk assessment frameworks, while regulators may use the findings to evaluate the effectiveness of mandatory disclosure policies. Second, this work contributes academically through increasing the literature on sustainability and firms' financial distress by providing evidence from an emerging market. Also, this study measures the ESG performance through the ESG score by using the FRA's decree no.108 which is a recent measure that is still underrecognized.

There are a few recommendations for future research presented as follows: (1) increasing the sample size which would improve the statistical power of the model, (2) using other detailed measurement for Sustainability performance such as the separate role of each ESG pillar in reducing financial distress, (3) explore the effect of applying the FRA's decree 108 as obligatory ESG disclosure on different financial variables within the firm, (4) future research may expand this analysis by examining sector-specific effects and crisis periods.

To conclude, the study is expected to contribute to the ESG and financial distress literature by extending the analysis to an emerging market context and by emphasizing on new measurements for the ESG performance.

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